

TOURISM FOR KIDS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7176174>

Ne'matullayeva Nodirabegim Nodirovna

O'zbekiston davlat jahon tillari talabasi

Ilmiy rahbar Baxtiyarov Muxtorjon Yakubovich

Abstract: *This article discusses the role of tourism in the economy and the benefits of kids' tourism.*

Keywords: *Kids, tourism, ecology, learning, vacation, travelling*

People travel for many different reasons, such as business and visiting family and friends. When people travel for pleasure they are called tourists. Tourism is the business of encouraging and supporting tourists. Many people go on vacation because they want a break from their everyday lives, or to experience a warmer climate. Others enjoy learning about different cultures, tasting new cuisines, and observing different lifestyles.

Tourism is the process of spending time away from home in pursuit of recreation, relaxation, and pleasure while using commercial services such as hotels and restaurants. People choose to travel or go on vacation for various reasons, including to get a break from everyday life, to experience a warmer climate, to learn about different cultures, to taste new cuisines, and to observe different lifestyles. Tourism often overlaps with other activities, interests, and processes, such as business or pilgrimages. This gives rise to shared categories, such as “business tourism” and “sports tourism.”

Since the late 1900s tourism has grown and become an important part of economies all over the world. This growth has occurred because in more economically developed countries (MEDCs) people's lifestyles have changed. They have more money and there are many more opportunities to travel than in the past. The cost of travel has also become cheaper with the rise of low-cost airlines.

Tourists bring a lot of money to the place they are visiting, so they are good for a nation's wealth, or economy [1-12]. Money from tourism can be used to build hospitals and schools, and the industry provides employment.

Many countries promote tourism by developing areas that will attract visitors. This development sometimes causes concern from environmentalists and local residents. Governments have to consider the advantages that come from the

economic development of an area with the need to conserve the environment. Some places are so popular with tourists they are in danger of being damaged or even destroyed by the visitors' actions. Noise and traffic pollution, littering, and the erosion of footpaths are just some of the environmental problems caused by tourists. For this reason, all popular tourist spots need to be managed carefully.

Children are naturally very curious about new countries and are excited to learn new things and always want to know more about the interesting places you can visit, the food you will taste or the activities you can enjoy abroad.

Tourism means people traveling for fun. It includes activities such as sightseeing and camping. People who travel for fun are called "tourists". Places where many tourists stay are called "resorts". Places that people go to for tourism are called tourist destinations.

There are a lot of reasons why people travel for fun:

- Some people travel to learn about the history or culture of a city or country, or learn about the people who live there, or their ancestors.
- People from cold places sometimes like to relax in the sun. Many people from the north of Europe or North America travel to warmer places and visit beaches.
- Some people travel to do an activity which they cannot do at home. There are lots of ski resorts in the mountains of Switzerland and Austria, and seaside resorts in Greece and other warm countries.
- People sometimes visit friends and family in another city or country.
- Finally, some people enjoy a change in scenery. City people go to forests or deserts, and vice versa.

Youth travel is becoming increasingly more important within global tourism. In the 1990s, it represented 15% of the tourism market, with it increasing to 20% in the last decade, and expected to reach 25% in the near future. Tour operators and travel agencies represent an important distribution, booking and promotional channel in youth travel, accounting for up to 80% of all bookings, with increasing trend of their usage by end customers. There are more than 16,000 student tour operators and travel agencies estimated in this market [13-25].

There are five benefits of sustainable tourism for kids:

Defense and love for nature can be the best context to learn together with kids. Ecological camps, games or gymkhana are some examples. In addition to helping your children enjoy everything we experienced and knew, they can benefit from holidays based on ecotourism, as these experiences offer them opportunities of:

Learning about wildlife: Sustainable tourism for kids not only allows small groups to visit nature, but also those that are managed by qualified persons, teach the kids to understand basic fundamentals of birds, insects, animals and plants of the region and their relation to an ecosystem in balance.

Raising awareness on environmental degradation: An extremely important component of ecotourism for kids is to raise awareness to future consumers on how to minimize waste, soil erosion, air and water pollution so as not to disturb the environment - lessons that will always remain in the child's memory and influence their future purchasing decisions.

Participating in conservation efforts: Whether by recording sea turtle behaviors or learning the destructive role of invasive plant species in the desert, eco-tourism for kids allows a deep understanding of the fragility of the natural world.

Focusing on depletion of natural resources: Whether it is learning about how countries are incorporating renewable energies or how an eco-lodge harnesses solar or wind power for its operations - ecotourism for kids teaches how the impact of tourism is affecting the sustainable development of resources and means of transport, and how many countries are focusing on low carbon technologies [26-30].

Exposure to culture: From learning new languages and cultures to tasting new foods, sustainable tourism for kids promotes the dissemination and protection of different cultural traditions and experiences that provide a lasting global vision for children.

REFERENCES:

1. Bozarov, E. B. (2021). ANALYSIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN. *Scientific progress*, 2(6), 213-216.
2. Bozarov, E., & Babayeva, L. (2021). TURIZM SOHASIDA KLASTERLARNING SAMARASI VA AHAMIYATI. *Scientific progress*, 2(6), 208-212.
3. Jabborova, Z. O. (2019). Historical Approach Essence in Determining Pedagogical Professional Competence and Its Level. *Eastern European Scientific Journal*, (1).
4. Ikramovich, R. Z. Z., Shukhratovna, Y. S., To'lqinovich, S. B., & Ibragimovna, B. L. (2021). Monetary Policy Of The Uzbekistan And Its

Improvement Ways In Implementing. *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government*, 27(1), 1551-1557.

5. Yakubova, S. S. (2021). ANALYSIS OF COUNTRY DEBT POLICIES AND ITS EFFECTIVE GOVERNANCE. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (3), 410-413.

6. G'ulomxasanov, E., Ruziyev, B., & Akramov, S. (2022). TURIZMDA DESTINATSIYA. *Scientific progress*, 3(1), 143-150.

7. Бабаева, Л. И., & Гуломхасанов, Э. М. (2022). ЛОГИСТИКА В ТУРИЗМЕ. *Scientific progress*, 3(1), 470-474.

8. G'ulomxasanov, E., Abdullayev, N., & Madina, L. (2021). Turizm Va Ta'lim: Holati Va Istiqboli. *Барқарорлик ва Етакчи Тадқиқотлар онлайн илмий журнали*, 1(6), 343-348.

9. Gulomxasanov, E., Amirova, F. S. Q., & Amirov, A. S. O. G. L. (2021). IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA ICHKI TURIZIMNING ORNI VA AHAMIYATI. *Scientific progress*, 2(6), 171-174.

10. Gulomkhasanov, E., & Rakhmatova, N. (2022). THE ROLE OF TASHKENT IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM. *Scientific progress*, 3(1), 183-188.